

D4.1

Interview guide and data on interviews conducted

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D4.1 Interview guide and data on interviews conducted

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Partner abbreviations	Full name
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway)
HI	Háskóli Íslands (University of Iceland)
LOBA	Loba (Portugal)
CHX	Crowd Helix (Ireland)
SVEN	Smart Venice (Italy)
DIGI	Digiotouch (Estonia)
ULEID	Leiden University (The Netherlands)
FARPL	Farplas Automotive (Türkiye)
BFH	Bern University of Applied Sciences (Switzerland)

Abbreviations

AI

HR

HRM

SSH

Meaning

Artificial Intelligence

Human Resources

Human Resources Management

Social Sciences and Humanities

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1 Executive Summary

This report describes the BIAS project's Work Package 4 "Ethnographies and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research" overall methodological approach, the work conducted in the first year of the approach (Stage 1), and the connection between Stage 1 and Stage 2 (remainder) of the fieldwork. Stage 1 primarily consists of dedicated fieldwork across multiple countries and settings, in order to gain deeper qualitative insight into HR practices, bias at work, technological forms of potential discrimination. The work done in WP4 will also inform the technological development (WP3) and stakeholder engagement (WP5) of the BIAS project. WP4 is grounded in social sciences and humanities (SSH) based research which places significant emphasis on ethnographic fieldwork, both as a means to gain an in-depth understanding of the state of AI in the European labour market and as a method to guide the development of new, socially responsible AI technology.

This report firstly provides a review of previous work on AI bias in previous research literature, and the BIAS projects expert interviews. It then introduces the methodological framework used for Stage 1 of the fieldwork, followed by an overview of the fieldwork conducted for that first stage and initial findings from the fieldwork. It then describes the link between Stage 1 and the newly termed "Stage 2" of the fieldwork which is ongoing as of the time of writing this report (see future deliverables D4.2 and D4.3 for full overviews over Stage 2 results). This is followed by next steps, before summarizing of the report.

2 Review of previous work on AI bias

2.1 Literature Review

AI systems have since their beginnings been dealing with the concept of “bias” (Jirauch, 1966, Caruana & Schaffer, 1988; Haussler, 1988). Bias in AI can be understood in several ways, e.g. as a preference for certain data, procedural workings, or outcomes of models. Hellström et al. (2020) in their paper “Bias in Machine Learning--What is it Good for?” e.g. describe how “different types of biases are connected and depend on each other” stating that there is “a complex relation between bias occurring in the machine learning pipeline that leads to a model, and the eventual bias of the model (which is typically related to social discrimination). The former bias may or may not influence the latter, in a sometimes bad, and sometime good way.” From a political side, Podesta’s (2014) White House report warning against the negative implications of Big Data technologies, as well as the European “Assessment list for Trust-worthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) published in 2018, by the European Commission’s High-Level Expert Group on AI, setting guidelines for AI has warned against harmful impacts. Discrimination in AI has been investigated by scholars from diverse disciplines. The discriminatory potential of and/or practices around these technologies have e.g. been studied in risk assessment for criminal recidivism (Angwin et al., 2016; Courtland, 2018; Green, 2018) and for custodial decisions (Burgess 2018), healthcare (Birzhandi and Cho 2023), in public personnel management (Cho et al. 2023), and in hiring algorithms (Bogen and Rieke 2018). Multiple studies point to the fact that algorithmic bias may either amplify existing bias, as in the case of Conditional Random Field (CRF) (Zhoa 2017) or credit scoring systems (Hurlin et al., 2021) or create new types of bias, as in the case of COMPAS risk assessment (Brackey 2019) or risk adjustment (RA) models (Zink and Rose 2021).

A recent scoping review conducted as part of the BIAS project show how the use of AI in recruitment and HRM includes "outreach, screening, assessment and coordination" (Rigotti and Fosch-Villaronga, 2024, 2) showing how AI can outperform humans in the screening process and enhance their performance in assessment and process coordination. On the other side, Black and Van Esch (2020), highlighting the growing importance of intangibles to the economy and hence the centrality of recruitment as a "top strategic concern" (p. 216), assert that it has now become essential for companies to use AI in recruitment, which they call Digital Recruiting 3.0. They argue that analogue recruiting, which relied solely on humans in the recruitment process, was plagued by anchoring, confirmation and similarity biases, which were assumed – though not proven – to be mitigated by the Digital Recruiting 3.0 turn. A recent umbrella review of the literature on AI use in recruitment indeed highlights a broad consensus that "AI has the potential to mitigate discrimination in personnel selection," as it is "perceived to be more fair and objective in comparison to hiring decisions based on human judgment", a conviction endorsed across AI industry marketing, the HRM literature, and discussions surrounding AI ethics (Seppala and Malecka, 2024). Yet, Seppala and Malecka (2024) assert that this belief mostly stems from depending on presumed “specific meanings of the concepts of rationality, bias, fairness, objectivity and AI” which the industry “accept as self-evident” (p.1, 3), and which are otherwise quite debatable. Looking back at initiatives to reduce BIAS, such as the ALTAI model (Ala-Pietilä et al. 2020), there are several initiatives both for use and improvement. Radclyffe et al. (2023) argues that political bodies and industry have a special responsibility for ALTAI to be widely adopted. Gavornik et al. (2022) e.g. suggests stakeholder involvement as a way to improve the model. The BIAS project is focused on conducting continued research into the different conceptions of bias, fairness, objectivity and other related concepts for different actors in different contexts, and what the involvement of AI in these contexts means to them.

2.2 Expert interviews from WP2

The qualitative work done in WP4 of the BIAS project builds on scoping expert interviews conducted in the project’s WP2. These expert interviews examined professional expertise and attitudes of AI and HR experts to map current practices of AI in HR management, more specifically

the recruitment of job applicants and management of workers/employees where the creation, identification and mitigation of diversity bias is concerned, in order for the project as a whole to get a good baseline understanding of AI bias in HR settings. A total of 71 individual interviews were carried out over a 6-month period (December 2022 to May 2023) in eight countries: Estonia, France, Iceland, Italy, Norway, Switzerland, The Netherlands, Turkey. The participants comprised 35 AI developers/experts and 36 HR managers/experts. There were 17 women and 18 men for the AI experts' category and 28 women and 8 men for the HR experts' category. The interviews were conducted both in-person and virtually with a three-part semi-structured interview guide developed by the Icelandic and Norwegian partners and broadly covering the occurrence of AI bias and bias mitigation strategies, the use of AI in recruitment and the use of AI in worker management.

The main conclusions of the findings are structured in three parts, as described below:

AI and bias:

- Societal biases are present in AI training data and thus lead to AI algorithms reiterating and reinforcing these biases.
- The underrepresentation or overrepresentation of certain groups in the training data leads to bias.
- AI bias could stem from a faulty AI model such as its margin of error and input parameters.
- There is the risk of AI developers and HR recruiters harboring unconscious bias that could affect algorithmic decision outcomes.
- Bias related to one's gender, race, ethnicity, nationality, origin, skin color, name, age, and disability were reported as the most common forms of diversity bias in recruitment.

AI and worker management and recruitment:

- Some organizations do not use AI for worker management and control partly due to privacy regulations, strong trade unions, desire for fairness, and cost of use.
- AI is more commonly used in larger companies and countries than in smaller ones.
- AI should be used to assist rather than control employees.
- Human intervention where AI is used is essential as there are aspects of the HR process beyond the scope of AI.
- Acceptable use of AI is contingent on transparency, human oversight, explainability, and conditions of safety and security.

Bias mitigation strategies:

- Developing a bias mitigation system
- Having diverse AI development and HR management teams
- Having diversity quotas during recruitment (without overlooking qualification and skill)
- Raising awareness of bias
- Examining the training data and anonymizing applicant data
- Transparency and human involvement

WP4 interviews explore deeper and builds on the more general findings of WP2 interviews, going more in depth in 4 of the project's focus countries (Iceland, Norway, Italy and Turkey). Whereas WP2 interviews focused on HR and AI experts only using 1 interview guide, WP4 interviews included employees managed by AI and representatives of civil society organisations using 4 different interview guides that were more in-depth for each participant category. Research questions in WP2 interviews were also different from those posed in WP4 interviews. This is because WP2 aimed to gain a general overview of AI bias and the use of AI in recruitment and management of workers. It sought to understand bias in AI training data, model and outcome, the

extent of production of AI application and use, as well as reasons for non-use in a European context.

WP2 interviews focused on the perception of experts on the use of AI in recruitment and management focusing on positive/negative use and acceptable/unacceptable use. It sought to know the kind of training AI experts at the university level and to gain knowledge on the type of training AI and HR experts would prefer to receive in a training course to inform the design of capacity building strategies in WP5. WP4 interviews in contrast are much more focused not just on a general occurrence of bias, but bias specific to the development of AI applications, recruitment and management processes. WP4 thus delves deeper into how bias could occur at diverse points of the AI development phase and in the phases of recruitment and management. By exploring the sources of training data, developer autonomy and criteria for selecting the data as well as criteria for parameter setting for the AI algorithm, it also seeks to highlight the kind of considerations AI and HR experts (or their companies) make or should have regarding for bias when designing, adopting or planning to adopt AI solutions for recruitment. WP4 also includes the role of trade unions and poses additional questions about AI ethics and the ethical responsibility of developer companies, automation and human oversight, the impact of AI use on workers' health and wellbeing, and consideration for the rights of workers where AI is used.

In general, the methodology of WP4 Stage 1 interviews is different from the WP2 interviews in the following two perspectives. First of all, the WP4 Stage 1 interviews focus on the individual practices while WP2 interviews are more related to mapping the status quo of the industry. WP4 Stage 1 interview asks questions in a more detailed way to collect data from situated activities, excavating real cases and the entanglement between human and technology in a much deeper sense. Secondly, compared with WP2 interviews that were mostly conducted online, onsite interviews in WP4 Stage 1 were prioritized and the methodology suggests interviews to be conducted in the participants' workplace. In this way, the WP4 Stage 1 interviews were more than semi-structured interviews, with more ethnographic observations on the field site during interviews. For a more thorough explanation of WP2 interviews, see the BIAS project report 2.1, and 2.3.

3 Interview methodology for WP4

WP4's qualitative research includes semi-structured in-depth interviews and practice-oriented ethnographic fieldwork, overall collecting and analyzing rich, context-specific qualitative data on the use and perception of AI-based tools for recruitment and HRM, as well as the conception of fairness and bias for different stakeholders. The stakeholder categories for interviews in WP4 are similar to the categories of stakeholders engaged in other project activities, such as co creation workshops and survey responders in WP2, and capacity building workshops in WP5, to ensure good knowledge transfer between WPs. Partner NTNU is responsible for fieldwork in Italy, Norway, and Türkiye. Partner HI (University of Iceland) is responsible for interviews in Iceland. NTNU and HI have joint responsibility for interviews in the Netherlands.

3.1 Revision and the split into two stages

The qualitative data collection conducted in WP4 is split in two stages. Stage 1 was conducted during August 2023 – March 2024, whereas Stage 2 is planned primarily from July 2024 (with some early fieldwork in Iceland starting already from April 2024). Stage 2 will be reported in in deliverable D4.2 but an initial description of the knowledge transfer between Stage 1 and 2 is described in section 4 of this report. This split into two stages was the result after the first periodic report review by experts appointed by the European Commission in January 2024. The reviewers recommended splitting the fieldwork into an initial phase that had focused more on individual interviews and focus on more on-site observational studies and deeper interviews for Stage 2. Originally, the project had aimed for qualitative interviews with a total of 365 informants, some on-site and some off-site. This was divided into the following categories: (1) AI developers (n ≥ 50 across Europe); (2) employers and HR personnel (n ≥ 90 across Norway, Iceland, Türkiye, Italy, and the Netherlands); (3) employees and workers' representatives (n ≥ 225) in the same five countries as group 2). Fieldwork size was planned equally between all countries, except for Iceland where the significantly smaller population was taken into account resulting in a smaller informant sample. The original plan for fieldwork can be seen in table 1 below, with a breakdown of the informant categories and the corresponding sample sizes by country:

Country	AI developers	HRM Employers	& Workers and worker reps	TOTAL
Iceland	≥50	≥10	≥25	≥35
Italy		≥20	≥50	≥70
Netherlands		≥20	≥50	≥70
Norway		≥20	≥50	≥70
Türkiye		≥20	≥50	≥70
TOTAL	≥50	≥90	≥225	≥365

Table 1 Original interview plan for BIAS informants

This was however modified, when the WP4 was advised and agreed to split the fieldwork into two stages, as described in section 4, by the EU reviewers. We will first describe here the methods and results of Stage 1 interviews.

3.2 Stage 1 interviews

The interviews for Stage 1 included primarily semi-structured in-depth one-on-one interviews as well as a selection of focus-group interviews. Semi-structured interviews are valuable qualitative research tools that provided researchers with the dual benefits of maintaining focus on a specific subject while also offering the freedom and flexibility to explore emergent themes during the interview process. In-person interviews were prioritized, as they offered opportunities to observe interviewees' non-verbal communication. Some digital interviews were performed if an in-person interview was impossible for logistical reasons or if the interviewee specifically requested it. The

fieldwork involved observations and situational mapping of the landscape of AI in recruitment and HRM processes. This included conducting semi-structured in-depth interviews with three distinct groups of interviewees: HR managers & employees, workers & worker representatives such as unions, and AI developers. Focus group interviews, for example, could be useful at the beginning of data collection to quickly map avenues of investigation to explore in future interviews or at the end of data collection to test provisional conclusions with several stakeholders. Additionally, companies sometimes requested that their employees be interviewed as a group rather than individually.

The first task in WP4 was to obtain ethical clearance, a process undertaken in both Norway and Iceland. Ethical clearance for research in Norway was successfully obtained on 15.08.2023 from the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (SIKT). The application for ethical clearance in Iceland is currently under review. Initially, researchers approached participants via the network of BIAS researchers. After the initial round of interviews with these participants, the snowball method was utilized to connect with subsequent groups of participants, as well as thorough mapping of potential informants. This method involved asking interviewees to help identify other individuals who could serve as relevant informants for the research. Additionally, researchers will leverage their own network to reach out to suitable informants. In Stage 1 interviewees were pre-sampled and selected based on their professional role, including managers, HR personnel, AI developers, and workers. These categories differ in terms of vulnerability. Participants belonging to groups that are marginalized in the job market are highly relevant to the BIAS project. In Stage 2 some we aim to further include case studies with job seekers, immigrant workers and employees in precarious situations. Particular attention will be given to recruitment strategies and situated knowledges (Kristensen and Ravn 2015). The research design will be adapted to avoid any potential harm and bridge the marginalization that participants may experience (Lewis et. al 2023).

3.3 The qualitative interview guides

The qualitative research conducted by WP4 in Stage 1 involved both semi-structured and focus group interviews, with three main participant profiles: AI technology developers, employers responsible for recruitment processes and/or HR practitioners, and workers & worker representatives. The initial phase of WP4 activities consisted of developing semi-structured interview guides tailored to these participant profiles (see Annex 1). The interview guides were designed to gather data on several assessment criteria included in the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI). The self-assessment criteria aim to help assist technology developers in their itinerary to develop ethical and trustworthy AI systems. They resort to the following seven requirements of Trustworthy AI specified in the Ethics Guidelines for trustworthy AI:

1. Human Agency and Oversight
2. Technical Robustness and Safety
3. Privacy and Data Governance
4. Transparency
5. Diversity, Non-discrimination and fairness
6. Societal and environmental well-being
7. Accountability

The interview guides include questions to ensure data collection especially on the requirement of diversity, non-discrimination and fairness. They also include questions regarding participants' preferences over autonomous or semi-autonomous decision-making in recruitment and HRM processes, which speak to the first requirement on human agency and oversight. Information on the 2nd requirement concerning technical robustness and safety, the 7th requirement on accountability, as well as the 4th requirement on transparency, is mostly gathered in AI developer's interview guide. Employer's and employee's interview guides also include questions that would yield to knowledge on how well participants are informed about the use of AI in recruitment and HRM processes, serving the need to gather data on user engagement in AI technologies. These

guides also include follow-up questions on the more technical aspects of AI systems, such as datasets used for training purposes, to be asked in case participants prove to be well informed on the technical aspects of AI systems. The following includes a general overview of the interview questions in each interview guide.

Three different interview guides targeted toward each stakeholder communities were created; to focus more on the relevant practices that how different stakeholders interact with AI tools. Questions regarding individual participants' educational and professional background, as well as their understanding to fairness and bias can be found in all three interview guides. These questions provide a general context of participants, also help interviewers gain an overview on the ethical valuations from different stakeholders. Beside this, other questions are more related to the specific practices of particular stakeholders, focusing on their recruitment-related behaviours to investigate how AI tools are produced, used, and the impact they have on certain groups. We incorporated the results of WP2 interviews and the current research on AI for HR from both academia and industry into the design of the interview guides. In the expert interviews, we collected the perception of AI and HR experts on bias pertaining to AI solutions as well as their use in recruitment and management of employees. As they all expressed the concern on AI repeating the existing societal bias and the human oversight on AI usage, we included more questions regarding AI ethics and bias mitigation strategies in the WP4 interview guides. When it comes to the employee perspective, rather than using AI to control workers, experts suggested using AI to assist employees' daily work. Based on that, we added questions on AI usage in recruitment as well as in workplace in the interview guide for employees, to get a better understanding towards employees' demands.

The interview guide for **employers and HR managers** encompasses questions related to the participant's educational and professional background, a typical recruitment process, the utilization of digital tools and/or AI in recruitment and HRM processes, their opinions regarding bias and fairness in recruitment and HRM processes, existing measures within their workplace to counter bias and discrimination, their views on the impact of AI on the labour market and how to mitigate bias in these processes.

The interview guide for **employees** comprises of questions pertaining to the educational and professional backgrounds of the participants, their experience with the recruitment process, their understanding of bias and fair treatment in recruitment processes, their perceptions of AI and/or digital tools in recruitment and HRM processes, their knowledge and opinions regarding human resource management approaches employed by their workplace, their concerns regarding fairness and bias in HRM, their views on best practices concerning the use of AI in recruitment and HRM processes, and their perspectives on the utilization of AI and digital tools in the workplace.

The interview guide for **AI developers** encompasses questions on the educational and professional backgrounds of the participants, their experiences in developing AI for recruitment and HRM processes, the training data utilized in algorithm training, the criteria employed in parameter selection for the algorithm, their comprehension of bias and fairness, both in general and in workplace contexts. Additionally, it explores their viewpoints on the presence of bias associated with the use of digital tools in recruitment and HRM processes, their considerations regarding bias and fairness (and their mitigation) in the development of AI tools, their overarching perspectives on AI ethics and ethical responsibilities of AI developers. Furthermore, it delves into their opinions regarding the rights of workers concerning AI implementations in HRM, and their insights on the most effective ways to employ AI in recruitment and HRM processes. Following the semi-structured interview methodology, these guides are not intended to be employed verbatim in the same order in all interviews. Instead, they serve as tools to maintain structure and guide the direction of the conversation.

3.4 Stage 1 fieldwork results

As of the “Stage 1 – Stage 2 reconfiguration” of WP4’s data collection work in Spring 2024, table 2 below shows the final status of Stage 1 interviews with fieldwork completed in Iceland, Norway, Türkiye, and Italy. Fieldwork in the Netherlands had not been planned as of the Stage 1-Stage 2 split, and in discussions with the Project Officer, it was decided that fieldwork in the Netherlands was prioritized directly into Stage 2 of more ethnographic fieldwork as a focus. The table also includes a breakdown by gender. This final result of Stage 1 ran according to plan, and facilitated also how as the main data collection is done by PhDs who have to complete mandatory coursework for half a year as per university regulations.

Country	Tech. Developers				HRM & Employers				Employees & Union Reprs.				Total
	M	F	Other	Total	M	F	Other	Total	M	F	Other	Total	
Iceland	10	1	0	11	7	5	0	12	3	18	0	21	44
Italy	1	0	0	1	5	12	0	17	1	4	0	5	23
Norway	8	6	0	14	3	14	1	18	0	5	0	5	37
Türkiye	0	0	0	0	1	10	0	11	6	5	0	11	21
Total	19	7	0	26	16	41	1	58	10	32	0	42	125

Table 2 Status fieldwork

3.5 Data elicitation and analysis

Elicitation and analysis serve distinct but interconnected roles in the research process. Elicitation involves the structured yet flexible engagement with participants to gather data that reveal the nuances of lived experiences. This process encompasses data collection methods such as semi-structured interviews and targeted inquiries that allow participants’ perspectives to shape the research trajectory. The primary aim of elicitation is to draw out relevant information that captures the complexity of individual and collective experiences. This also encompasses choosing who to interview, with a broad scoping of potential interviewees, which the data gatherers make contact with. We follow an explorative approach, following the complexity of hiring and AI used in that context. The data collections are targeting specific personal parameters in their research (gender in Iceland, age in Italy, ethnicity in Norway, and LGBTQ+ individuals in Turkey). Furthermore, this method relies heavily on participants’ subjective interpretations, which may introduce inconsistencies or biases that challenge the generalizability of findings.

Analysis, on the other hand, involves systematically examining and coding the elicited data to identify patterns, themes, and conceptual relationships. We primarily use a grounded theory framework (Foley et al., 2021) as an analytical framework and a “way of thinking about and conceptualizing data” (Strauss and Corbin, 1994: 275) which envisages theory formation or construction grounded in qualitative data (Charmaz 2014; Conlon et al., 2015; Bryant, 2020). This method e.g encompasses open coding of qualitative data in an iterative move between data collection, data coding and memo-writing. We use theoretical sampling, which according to Foley et al. (2021: 1), is a core feature of grounded theory, not only encompassing “sampling participants with a set of theoretical considerations in mind”, but also occurring within the data generation process through interviewing. By conducting targeted inquiries into thematic domains and engaging in analysis in field settings to introduce variation and depth into the analytical framework is key for this next step. Theoretical sampling, therefore, entails a gradual progression towards sampling participants based on emerging themes within data and concepts that are produced during the iterative analysis. We thus see the development of theoretical understandings of the data as core outcomes of the analysis, which feed into Stage 2, and the further knowledge transfer between WP4 and the other relevant project WPs. One example of this is how Stage 1 qualitative interviews in Norway has led to knowledge of immigrant populations facing severe language issues when applying for jobs, which has then been important for shifting

the elicitation process towards this vulnerable group. The importance of theoretical sampling within grounded theory forms the basis for the preference for unstructured or semi-structured interviews. This affords autonomy and flexibility to the interaction between the researcher and participants, facilitating the co-construction of the interview process, and the exploration of emergent concepts. Both [Foley et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Conlon et al. \(2015\)](#) endorse the use of semi-structured interviews in grounded theory studies, especially when specific domains have already been identified for further investigation. This aligns with our research within the BIAS project, where our goal is to gain a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape of AI implementations in recruitment and HRM processes across Europe. This includes examining existing and emerging (AI-based) biases and discriminations, as well as strategies for mitigating bias in AI-mediated recruitment and HRM processes.

Together, elicitation and analysis allow for a dynamic process wherein insights gained through early analysis can influence subsequent elicitation efforts, refining the research focus and enabling a richer, more layered understanding of the phenomenon under study.

3.6 Preliminary findings from Stage 1 in Iceland

For Stage 1, 44 interviews were conducted in Iceland. 25 interviews were conducted with employees comprising 7 HR experts, 11 AI experts and 7 representatives within civil society organisations (trade unions and NGOs). A field study was then undertaken with two fishing companies within 3 fishing factories (case studies 1-3) that employ AI in their fish processing and for monitoring and evaluation of their employees' performance with and without the reward of extra bonuses. This resulted in observations of the processing of the fish along with 19 interviews, 5 with HR management and 14 with employees working directly on the fish processing line. Findings from the individual interviews showed that AI is not as widely used in Iceland for recruitment although workers in the white colour sector use AI for some part of their management processes, mostly to optimise their work, such as scheduling meetings, managing work and personal schedules, assistive writing and spell checks (because English is a second language to most). AI developers reported that bias does indeed emanate from the training data and AI model, most AI applications are already pre-trained with data from big data companies that include data from the internet, some AI applications are trained with historical company data. They also pointed out that developers have high autonomy when building their AI systems, such as deciding on training data and setting parameters to train the AI model. Bias was said to occur at these two points.

It was also found that most AI tools are developed with no consideration for bias. AI developers believed they had an ethical responsibility to ensure they use fair data, and that they are transparent about their AI systems and its limitations. It was said that a lot of AI products marketed barely do all they claim, and a lot are not even AI, just simple algorithms. HR experts mentioned that affinity and confirmation biases on the part of recruiters could impact the recruitment process unfairly. Also, bias can occur during job advertisement, screening, assessment, interview and selection phases of the recruitment process. According to them few companies consider bias when using AI tools and HR practitioners put a lot of trust in these tools. All participants advocated for human oversight, transparency, respect for workers' rights, fairness and the ability to question decision where AI is used. They concurred that AI should be used to assist rather than monitor and control employees, it impacts the wellbeing, health, security and safety of employees, causing stress, anxiety, loss of autonomy and control. With regards to workers' rights, they thought AI monitoring breached workers right to privacy; workers had a right to know whether and how they are monitored with AI and should be able to opt out of this way of monitoring. Many of the participants representing civil societies felt that bias mitigation should be a process engrained into an organisation and considered at all phases of the recruitment and management of workers. Trade unions were also said to advocate for proper implementation of AI legislations to protect workers rights. Lastly it was said that organisations should aptly prepare when adopting AI solutions such as preparing and training their staff.

In the fishing factories the field study aimed to mostly explore the experiences of workers with the introduction of more high-tech machines that more thoroughly scrutinised how they clean the fish on the trimming/assembly lines. It was also to explore how the introduction of a bonus scheme impacted or was likely to impact them (two factories had a bonus system and one did not). Emphasis was placed on the wellbeing and health of workers, particularly stress and strain as well as safety and security. Workers described their wellbeing and health in terms of their psychological wellbeing attributed to levels of stress, physical wellbeing associated with reported bodily, back and shoulder pain, and social wellbeing in relation to their interpersonal relations. In the fish factories that had upgraded to more high-tech AI powered machines, most workers preferred the older system of working as they felt they were less stressed because the work was slower and easier on their bodies. They reported having to work twice or more now than before which added to their stress. Some also longed for the old system for it was a time where they had time to interact more with each other. A few workers from the factory felt they were less stressed because the work had become easier due to the automation of a huge part of the manual labour. In all cases, the new system of working was viewed as safe and secure and not a source of stress for workers. Stress/strain was the most recurring wellbeing issue raised by all workers attributed to fast paced work, the mode of performance monitoring, evaluation and rewards schemes, and limited workplace interaction. When comparing the experience of workers whose performance accrued extra bonuses with those whose performance did not, the former seemed to experience more stress and complained more about their physical health. They also felt the measurement for deciding their extra bonuses was another source of stress for them as they felt the urge to work faster to avoid falling behind their colleagues. The latter admitted that should they be put on a bonus scheme they would equally feel more stressed. Competitiveness amongst workers were reported in all factories.

3.7 Preliminary findings from Stage 1 in Italy

In Italy, during Stage 1, a total of 17 individual and group interviews have been conducted with 17 HR practitioners, 5 workers' representatives and 1 AI developer. From these interviews it emerged the picture of a context characterized by a lack of specialized talent which leads to a high number of unqualified candidates for many job postings. AI is considered by interviewees to be potentially useful in doing first screenings, however, HR departments are believed to be highly change-averse and not very innovative. Nevertheless, many interviewees working in HR have experimented with AI for different tasks and see the potential of the technology. When it comes to the specifics of the selection process, Italian HR practitioners believe AI to be useful in the first screening phases but think that human intervention remains fundamental at later stages, especially for interviews and the final selection. It must be noted, however, that within HR departments it is usually junior employees who perform the initial screening and senior recruiters intervene only afterwards. AI use could, thus, present differences between junior and senior HR practitioners. In addition, HR practitioners often mentioned a fear of replacement against which they adopted different tactics to protect themselves and redefine their profession.

Regarding issues of bias, gender and ethnicity bias have been identified by the interviewees as the most well-known problems. Gender bias is being strongly addressed at the national level through increased public incentives for gender equality which meant that many interviewed HR practitioners were developing gender equality strategies at the time of being interviewed. Workers' representatives also indicated gender bias as an important concern, intersected with other types of biases. Ethnicity bias, on the other hand, while mentioned, is a much smaller concern for HR practitioners. Ethnicity bias is often masked behind language proficiency or cultural fit, which results in a lower percentage of foreigners being hired. Other characteristics also emerged as potentially leading to bias and one in particular is perceived by HR practitioners as persistent which is age bias. Italian companies retain strict hierarchical organizations and, as a result, age is often a discriminating factor. Candidates who are too young might not be considered for some positions, but also candidates who are considered too old and experienced for a job will be disadvantaged. In the light of this perception, Italian HR practitioners generally believed to be less biased than AI due to their better understanding of the company's context and culture. This leads

to a fear of algorithmic bias. For example, many HR practitioners were aware of the risks of using historical data to train hiring algorithms and voiced against this practice. The opportunities of hiring algorithms were believed to lie in the higher accuracy they would provide thanks to data-driven decisions.

3.8 Preliminary findings from Stage 1 in Norway

In Norway, 37 interviews were conducted during the Stage 1, including 14 interviews with developer side, 18 with HR practitioners and 5 workers. The participants from developer sides did not only involve developers that directly work with technical production, but also salesperson, managers, and CEOs of developer companies. The HR community covered HR officers both from public and private sectors, head-hunters and people that work in recruitment consultancy business. There were also several interviews with hiring managers in different companies. Last but not the least, workers interviewed in Stage 1 were all with immigrant backgrounds, and most of them were not EU/EEA citizens. From developer side, a lot of digital products have been developed to tackle the issue on equity, diversity and inclusion in the workplace. Although people showed an increasing interest in AI, and AI-based product has already been put into market to help mitigate human bias throughout the hiring process, there were still debates on whether AI is trustworthy enough to apply in human resource management. Some developers showed a deep concern towards AI and insisted on not applying AI to their product to ensure fairness and explainability. Instead of treating AI as the core function, more developer companies integrate AI, mainly GPT, in their already existing platforms as an add-on. The current AI tools on the markets were mainly targeted on the initial stage of hiring process, including job description writing, resume summarizing, initial screening and further candidates' selections for interviews.

From the HR perspective, although AI hasn't been officially introduced in the HR domain in some companies, many HR officers have tried to use AI (ChatGPT) to facilitate their work. Compared with the organizational implementation, AI usage among HR officers is more individual oriented. HR practitioners have asked AI to help them come up with new ideas on workshop organizing, interview questions and job ad formatting, but they claimed that HR officers themselves were always the final decision maker in the human-AI interaction to ensure fairness. Meanwhile, AI also brings new requirements on HR officers' digital literacy, that they need to equip themselves with knowledge on how to use AI, in other words, how to give proper prompt. Some HR officers learned themselves, others organized workshops to experiment AI together with their colleagues, to enhance their expertise in the AI age. The interviews with employees and workers reveal the challenges and barriers that people ran into during job seeking. As candidates, they were not quite sure if the employer company has used AI during hiring processes. It was not very common for recruiters to reject them with a very specific reason, but the candidates could also come up with several reasons on why they (not) got the job. People with immigrant ground were more likely to link the rejection with their ethnicity or language skills, and they also found it difficult to grasp the idea of "cultural fit".

3.9 Preliminary findings from Stage 1 in Türkiye

In Türkiye, 22 semi-structured in-depth one-to-one interviews were conducted with employees (11) and HR professionals (11). A preliminary content analysis (Julien, 2008) was conducted on the interview transcripts to identify central themes that would guide the second phase of the research. AI-based technologies have started to be employed in Türkiye's labor market, especially in candidate selection processes during the recruitment phase. Several companies, acting as third-parties or vendors, have launched AI-based digital services to assess and evaluate potential candidates, and streamline hiring processes. A quantitative study on human resource managers and employees in Türkiye's 500 largest companies in terms of capital (Kambur and Akar, 2021) indicates that "the human resource managers and employees of the Turkey's largest 500 companies in terms of capital have a medium level of knowledge about AI" and "52% of them actively use AI in any part of their companies, and 30% in the human resource department" (p. 197). This study underlines the need to conduct qualitative studies comparing human decision-

making processes with that of AI, a gap in the literature which will be covered by BIAS Project WP4 activities.

According to the qualitative content analysis, the most common types of bias in Türkiye during the recruitment phase included a. university bias, b. regional bias, c. gender bias, and d. bias based on gender expression and/or identity. University bias includes positive bias towards graduates of a number of top universities in the country (namely Boğaziçi University (BU), Middle East Technical University (METU), Sabancı University and Koç University). Regional bias includes reported positive bias towards potential employees who come from the same city and/or region as the responsible manager, gender bias mostly appears as a consequence of gender segregation in occupations, resulting in gendered occupations and positions. Finally, gender expression and/or identity refers to bias against individuals who have gender expressions and/or identities that do not conform to assumed sex-based gender characteristics. Most respondents were positive about the potential of AI to address these biases, particularly in the initial selection phase. There was a general belief that AI would be more objective. However, they all agreed on the need for a 'human touch', especially in the later stages of the recruitment process.

4 From Stage 1 to Stage 2

As described previously in this report, the project decided to split the fieldwork into two stages, as per the reviewers' suggestions. In Stage 2, we focus less on individual semi-structured interviews, and more on case-ethnographies. Ethnography is a type of qualitative research method used in SSH to investigate communities, cultures, and practices, is increasingly being applied to analyze technology design, development and adoption within the AI domain (e.g. [Fischer, Östlund and Peine, 2020](#), [Henriksen and Blond, 2023](#)). Ethnographic study of algorithms has e.g. been studied by critical scholars such as [Seaver \(2017\)](#) valuing the importance of grounding studies in empirical research. Ethnographic methods offer a rich understanding of the sociotechnical realities surrounding various aspects and actors involved in the design, development, and adoption of AI technologies.

With these concerns in mind, the activities of WP4 revolve around conducting ethnographic fieldwork across Europe to harness this potential. In our cases, we gather insights into how employees and managers work with AI technology by observing and interacting with people in their work environments. By watching work performance and interaction with AI tools, we aim to build on the knowledge from interviewees in stage one, furthering our understanding of the employees' and managers' behaviours and how the technology is used in practice. We also interview the workers at their workplace and get their views on the AI tools and how they affect work performance. We take field notes about interactions, behaviours, and the environmental context. Since we are getting close to the activity itself, and some of the participants are in vulnerable situations, such as job seekers or individuals who are easily fired, if they express themselves about the workplace and AI technology in a way that the owners or management do not like, BIAS researchers respect their privacy by strictly ensuring ethical integrity in research (see e.g. [Creswell, 2007](#)).

To facilitate this deeper focus in Stage 2, we are focusing on distinct case studies – which are further described by country in the next sections. We do point out that these are plans, which might change due to availability, and results of analysis from Stage 1. The case studies to be conducted in Stage 2 builds on insights and preliminary analysis of data collected in Stage 1 and will accordingly focus on phenomena identified as particularly relevant to pursue and cover a broad range of groups engaging with AI, across different types of companies and industries. The selection of cases is rooted in the country specific contexts, however also carefully developed to enable comparative investigations where relevant. Stage 2 will include more extensive fieldwork in selected sites for each case, allowing for rich contextual knowledge as this is arguably crucial to enhance the understanding of how technologies may play out differently in different contexts ([Mayrhofer et. al 2019](#)). Data collection in Stage 2 will thus be coordinated through exchange of preliminary findings to allow for comparative analysis across national contexts.

4.1 Case studies in Iceland

Iceland will focus on three case studies. The first is a fishing company who has adopted an extra bonus scheme, a second case in another company will focus on the adoption of an extra bonus system, and a third focus will be with another fishing company that is not planning to adopt an extra bonus system, to have a 3-way comparison. These studies will explore workers experience with the change in their work processes and monitoring of their productivity due to the introduction of high-tech AI machines emphasizing perception of work before and after the introduction of the new machines, their wellbeing, health and safety. It would equally focus on stress and strain, and explore their thoughts on an extra bonus system, competitiveness, interpersonal relations, fairness, and ways they feel their work or wellbeing could be improved.

4.2 Case studies in the Netherlands

In the Netherlands case studies will focus on recruitment and management. The approach to management would take a similar form as the fish factories to explore workers experience on AI

monitoring and performance evaluation. The approach to recruitment would focus on an aspect of the recruitment process such as assessment and interviews where AI applications are used wholly or partly. It will explore the experience of workers and the occurrence of bias. It will also explore diversity, equity and inclusion strategies of the companies and further explore concepts from the individual interviews such as AI ethics and regulation, bias and fairness, rights of workers, wellbeing and health, safety and security as well as the responsibility of organisations when adopting AI ethics. These aspects would be incorporated into interviews (already part of existing interview guides) with AI experts, HR practitioners and employees within a single organisation utilising AI in their recruitment and/or management processes.

4.3 Case studies in Italy

The Italian case studies are by writing the most advanced, as agreements have been made with organizations. We have thus crystalized three distinct cases as described below:

Case study 1 – HR intuition

This case study will focus on HR practitioners' interactions with AI through their understanding of their expertise. From Stage 1 interviews, it emerged that HR practitioners, especially senior recruiters, when selecting an applicant often rely on intangible and incommunicable expertise, sometimes linked to a “gut feeling” or intuition. However, this intuition is considered specifically human and difficult to translate to an AI. Relying on this specific professional intuition can be both a sign of reflexivity and awareness of one’s own biases, or an expedient for hiding one’s biases behind the label of “intuition”. The introduction of AI adds a further layer of complexity, leading to different uses of AI depending on how HR practitioners evaluate their own intuition and professional identity. The interpretation of new technologies has been found to be influenced by professional identity (Nelson and Irwin, 2014), additionally in this case different AI uses might lead to different outcomes regarding bias and diversity.

Stage 2 will focus on investigating further the nature of HR expertise and how it shapes their interaction with AI systems. How do they negotiate their professional identity in the light of AI adoption in HR? And what consequences does this have for diversity and inclusion in hiring? This will be done through interviews and observations with senior recruiters using AI for any step of the recruitment and selection process. Considering the influence of professional socialization in shaping professional identity, interviews with University Professors in HRM will also be conducted and a university level course in HRM will be followed.

Case study 2 – Generational Differences

This case study will focus on the differences in AI use between junior and senior recruiters. During Stage 1 interviews, a power difference between HR practitioners subtly emerged. In interviews with senior recruiters, it was mentioned that the task of screening candidates is often done by junior recruiters first, and only later senior recruiters intervene. During group interviews, the junior employees were usually the ones doing the “dirty work” of recruiting candidates and, when used, more apt in the use of AI systems. Junior HR practitioners often seemed to be more practical in their approach to AI and open to experimentation. The use and perception of AI by junior employees might be different than their bosses also due to their greater closeness with the AI and potential threat. Previous literature also shows how status-differences in organization influence AI use (Anthony, 2018). Considering the ambiguous position of HR units in private companies, which in Italy have only gained authority in the past ten years, status differences play a key role both within and outside of HR departments.

Stage 2 will focus on investigating junior HR and HR in training and their use and perception of AI for their profession compared to senior HR (part of the previous case study). Is their perception and use of AI different? And how does this impact the selection process, in which junior and senior HR perform different tasks? This will be investigated through interviews and observations with junior recruiters using AI for any step of the recruitment and selection process and through interviews with HRM students. Generational differences are a known parameter for different digital

literacy and technology use, however, how this plays out in the context of HR is yet to be investigated.

Case study 3 – AI narratives and HR futures

This case study will focus on the relationship between popular AI narratives and HR's understanding of the technology for their profession. During Stage 1 interviews, when asked about their imagined future of AI for HR, interviewees always directly or indirectly addressed a fear of replacement. Interviewees did not always have this fear themselves, but they understood it to be a popular fear which they needed to address. In doing so, interviewees often relied on existing discourses of upskilling and reskilling which are a very common response within the public discourse to fears of replacement (Ulnicane, 2022). Nevertheless, they also responded to these concerns by highlighting those human characteristics which they think are non-replaceable by an AI and the core to their specific profession of HR. The way in which they imagined AI futures thus, influenced their own willingness to try the technology and for what tasks. While HR practitioners understand their own role regarding AI replacement, they are heavily influenced by the popular narrative around them.

Stage 2 will delve further into the relationship between popular AI narratives and imaginaries and how HR practitioners' understanding and use of AI is influenced by them. What is the popular imaginary concerning AI for work? And how does it influence HR people's decisions about AI use? How do HR people negotiate their own expertise and professional identity on the backdrop of AI development? This will be investigated through focus groups with HR practitioners and through content analysis of materials from relevant AI-HR products and of practitioners' outlets (for example HR Link and AIDP – *Associazione Italiana Direttori del Personale*) to understand the specific AI narratives to which HR practitioners are exposed.

All three case studies are complementary with one another, meaning that data collection will not happen strictly separately, but all three cases will inform each other and build on each other throughout the process.

4.4 Case studies in the Netherlands

As the Dutch fieldwork had not started by the time the Stage 1 and Stage 2 distinction was decided, the PI has in discussion with the PO agreed that Stage 1 should be skipped for this country, focusing more deeply on Stage 2 work.

Case study on AI developer company

During the Stage 1, we conducted our fieldwork in one of the biggest HR technology conferences – the EU HR technology 2024 conference held in Amsterdam. In this 2-day conference, we joined many seminars on the topic of AI and met a lot of HR technology vendors from all over the world. Among all the digital solutions, one major perspective is to leverage digital technology for fairness and EDI (equity, diversity and inclusion) initiatives in companies. Several vendors have provided such applications, both with AI and without AI embedded in their core technology. When it comes to the reason why AI technology is (not) inscribed in their service, both sides have firm explanations on how AI will facilitate/impede fairness in workplaces. Such diverse understanding towards AI and fairness was also revealed through the interviews with developers from different companies, that they interpreted differently on the relationship between AI and fairness.

To further explore how developers understand fairness and bias and operationalize their ideas in their product, we choose a developer company as our field site in the Stage 2, planning to stay with their research & development teams to learn more about the development of AI fairness product. It is a Dutch company that produce AI product for hiring, with a focus on fairness and human bias mitigation. I will stay there for one month, joining their internal meetings as well as meetings with their clients, to conduct observation and interviews on the developer community. Besides their daily working practices, what is more interesting here is the transforming and changes happened in the developer company, and how they clarify the necessity of AI usage in hiring practices.

Sample research questions:

- How is the AI solution made to solve ethical issues in the workplace? How do developers operationalize fairness (EDI) in their product?
- What are unintended and unexpected implications of “fairness-by-design”?
- Why do they (not) apply AI in their product? How do these choices entangle with domain knowledge, other stakeholders and relevant social discourses?
- How do they shift their idea on AI when they get different feedbacks from clients?

4.5 Case studies in Norway

Norwegian fieldwork will have a focus on immigrant workers/job seekers. In the Stage 1, although there were not many interviews with stakeholders from this community, common trends could be found from the workers’ experiences. As the interviews were mostly conducted with immigrants in Norway, participants mostly shared their struggles on the lack of social network, the miscommunication on the concept of “cultural fit”, and the language skills required from the employers. Another trace that is worth following is that some participants mentioned that they were using AI (ChatGPT) to help them look for a job, including proofreading their cover letter and rehearsing interviews.

Based on the preliminary finding from Stage 1, Stage 2 case study in Norway will thus mainly focus on the worker/employee group, including people who already found a job as well as people who are currently looking for a job. I will mainly recruit participants who are not from EU/EEA region, with their background as immigrants in Norway. More specifically, participants from sensitive national backgrounds, who do not only face the challenge as an foreign immigrant but also struggle with geopolitical limitations. For example, in some job ads, they will highlight that Chinese and Iranian citizen will be excluded in the very beginning because of the national security reasons. To conduct the fieldwork, researchers will shadow at least 5 immigrant job seekers for 1-2 days each (McDonald & Simpson, 2014), taking notes on their job-seeking practices and their usage of AI-powered tools. During the shadowing, formal and informal interviews will also be conducted to know more about their thoughts on fair hiring, AI for hiring, and their expectation towards the AI leverage from the employer company. Sample research questions:

- What are the struggles and barriers the immigrant in Norway face? How do they perceive fairness and other values through the job-seeking processes?
- how do these groups leverage AI themselves to increase their chances in the labour market?
- How does the technology used by recruiters influences their practices and perceptions?
- How do job seekers approach the hiring process differently when they realize the employer company is using AI for hiring?

4.6 Case studies in the Türkiye

Two case studies have been identified for Türkiye. The first will focus on the preliminary content analysis in Stage 1 revealed that gender expression and/or identity was one of the most significant biases in the country during the recruitment phase. It was also observed during the preliminary interview phase that LGBT+ people face serious challenges both during and after the recruitment phase, as most of them have to remain in the closet. As a result, it is observed that they are over-represented in the few companies in Istanbul that are known to be LGBT+ friendly. I plan to conduct fieldwork in one of these companies and interview the LGBT+ employees about their job search experiences, their opinions on fairness in recruitment and HRM, and the integration of AI in these processes. The second case study will be focusing on that in Istanbul, the integration of AI in recruitment processes has followed a rapid pace, especially after the pandemic. In fact, it is recorded that “Istanbul has remarkably started using AI in its human resources on a routine basis” (Nicoleta et al. 2022). There are several third-party companies that provide AI-based recruitment and HRM tools to companies. I plan to visit two of these companies for about a week to make

field observations of how they a. design and develop, b. market their products. An important aim will be to observe how they consider the potential AI bias of their tools and, if so, how they try to mitigate it.

4.7 ALTAI principles and case studies

The Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) requirements have been created in 2020 by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence to provide AI developers and deployers with a practical checklist for developing trustworthy AI. This use of the ALTAI requirements has been integrated into WP4 Stage 1 and Stage 2 activities with AI developers. Specifically, interview questions to AI developers during Stage 2 focus on their understanding of the “diversity, non-discrimination and fairness” requirement and how they translate it into AI systems. Therefore, interview guides for AI developers include questions about datasets used and their origin, AI training algorithms, fairness concepts, and stakeholders’ engagement. This will provide insights into developers’ awareness of ALTAI requirements of “diversity, non-discrimination and fairness” as well as “transparency” and “accountability” and their relevance to AI products for hiring.

Nevertheless, ALTAI’s requirements relevance for developers have already been established in the moment of their creation. Therefore, WP4 Stage 2 activities aim at providing additional knowledge regarding users’ priorities for trustworthy AI and the influence of their use onto the fairness of the technology. In fact, while attention to datasets and training algorithms is important to ensure AI fairness, completely unbiased data are impossible to obtain. Contextual knowledge is needed to understand which dimension is important in which context and which could lead to bias. HR practitioners conscious use of AI systems is as important as AI development. Therefore, Stage 2 will focus, first, on assessing whether compliance with ALTAI requirements is enough for an AI system to be considered trustworthy by users (recruiters, employees, and job seekers in this case). Questions about fears connected to AI, perception of AI’s impact on diversity and fairness, experience with AI use will be asked to understand the ALTAI’s requirements importance from a user’s perspective. Secondly, observing HR practitioners’ interactions and oversight of AI systems will unveil to what extent human oversight is needed, to what extent HR practitioners are aware of this need, and their willingness to collaborate with AI instead of merely delegating to it.

This dimension will also be investigated through job seekers’ experiences. Understanding whether compliance with ALTAI is sufficient for them to make a comfortable use of AI and trust companies using it or whether they still have fears connected to AI use. Therefore, we will investigate vulnerable people’s experience as employees managed with the support of AI systems and as job seekers selected through AI. Lastly, Stage 2 will also provide insights into how they themselves are aware of AI risks and their role in mitigating them. For example, observing if they adopt strategies for writing “AI-friendly” CV and cover letters or try to influence recommendation systems in AI-powered platforms for hiring, like LinkedIn.

The ALTAI requirements of “diversity, non-discrimination and bias”, “transparency”, “accountability” and “human agency and oversight” are thus integrated into the core research questions of Stage 2 case studies. In fact, transparency and human oversight are two key characteristics for ensuring non-discrimination. Sufficient transparency and human oversight will also lead to clearer accountability measures, allowing for auditability and monitoring if needed. Understanding how “diversity, non-discrimination and bias” requirements are integrated into AI systems and perceived by users will lead to understanding the role “transparency”, “human agency and oversight” and “accountability” play for this purpose.

Regarding “technical robustness and safety” and “privacy and data governance”, two ALTAI requirements, WP4 Stage 2 case studies will assess their importance for establishing trust in AI systems among users. Both requirements are subject to precise and strict regulations at EU and national levels which make them the norm for AI developers. Observing AI use by recruiters, job seekers, and employees, we will assess whether technical robustness of the systems and data privacy play a role in determining AI use and trustworthiness.

Lastly, the “environmental and societal wellbeing” requirement infuses all Stage 2 case studies through their focus on AI impact on the recruitment process. WP4 activities will support discovering insights regarding AI impact on the HR profession and on all professions, which could be subject to recruitment through AI systems. First, HR practitioners will be asked about their perceived impact of AI on their own profession and how the use of AI influenced their professional identity and the future of HR. Secondly, Stage 2 data case studies overall will assess the impact of AI systems of recruitment practices informing AI impact on the job market. By gathering insights of this nature, WP4 research will help inform further elaboration on the ALTAI requirement of “environmental and societal wellbeing” for the specific case of hiring, providing concrete ways in which AI could impact human work and the workforce.

Overall, the ALTAI requirements have been integrated into the design of Stage 1 interview guidelines with a focus on “diversity, non-discrimination and bias” which we will expand on in Stage 2 considering both the developers’ and users’ perspectives. Our design of Stage 2 case studies considers all ALTAI requirements as a basis for investigating fairness in AI in the specific context of HR and recruitment.

5 Next steps

When writing the initial report, fieldwork was still ongoing, and many uncertainties due to informant access and case mappings persisted. As of the writing of this revised version, WP4 has done the described and requested split into two stages of fieldwork, where Stage 1 fieldwork interviews has concluded its data collection and is in ongoing data analysis, which has also informed the Stage 2 fieldwork ethnographies which are ongoing for Autumn 2024. To illustrate this, we provide our activity plan in table 3 below:

	2023	2024		2025		2026	
	Fall	Spring	Fall	Spring	Fall	Spring	Fall
Reports:	D4.1 delivered 31.10.23		D4.1 revised delivered 31.10.24	D4.2 due 30.04.25		D4.3 due 30.04.26	
Fieldwork:	Stage 1 fieldwork		Stage 2 fieldwork	Analysis and knowledge transfer of fieldwork results to other WPs.			

Table 3 WP4 Revised timeline

Stage 1 transcription, anonymization and analysis are well underway and done as Stage 2 fieldwork has begun. As qualitative research, particularly within the grounded theory framework, is an iterative process, we build on knowledge as it is uncovered by the project participants. This means that data collection through interviews and field observations, as well as data analysis, occurs concurrently, with the latter informing subsequent stages of data collection. Preliminary concepts and themes emerging from this initial data of Stage 1 analysis thus help guide the next round of Stage 2 ethnographies. In doing so, researchers are discussing the employment of theoretical frameworks, including situated knowledge method in feminist science and technology studies, sociology of work and employment, phenomenological approaches to work life. This period will also witness further work on data analysis, including discussion regarding the role of inductive analysis within grounded theory. Additionally, the forthcoming period will entail the implementation of the Data Management Plan, which will involve making the final decision regarding the storage location for anonymized interview transcriptions. The fieldwork of Stage 2 is set to take place in Autumn 2024, with fieldwork trips of several months each planned by the PhDs and postdocs gathering data. This will be fully described in the following WP4 reports.

6 Summary

This report has described the work conducted under Work Package 4 (WP4) of the BIAS project, titled “Ethnographies and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) Research.” In the report we have described the focuses on the overall methodological approach, the work completed in the first phase (Stage 1), and the connection between Stage 1 and Stage 2. Stage 1 involved extensive fieldwork across four countries to gain qualitative insights into HR practices, workplace bias, and potential technological discrimination. The findings from WP4 has aimed to inform both technological development in WP3 and stakeholder engagement in WP5 within the broader scope of the BIAS project. The SSH-based research in WP4 emphasized ethnographic fieldwork to deepen the understanding of AI’s role in European labour markets and to guide the development of socially responsible AI technology. The report has highlighted the methodologies we have chosen to further understand biases in labour markets and the state of AI implementation in recruitment and HRM practices across different countries in Europe, and described the interview guides developed for each stakeholder focused on. The report also outlined the initial WP4 interview plans for Stage 2 cases. Overall, the report provided a comprehensive update on the methodologies and progress of WP4, setting the stage for continued research and analysis in the next phase of the BIAS project.

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Annex 1 – Interview guides

SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW GUIDE

EMPLOYERS

Introduction

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. We are interviewing you to better understand the recruitment and human resource management processes in your company, the way you understand fairness and bias in these processes, the extent to which you resort to digital tools to manage them and your opinions on the way these tools can affect the fairness of the recruitment and HRM processes. There are no right or wrong answers to any of our questions, we are interested in your own experience.

We have an information sheet and a consent form for you to undersign. [Hand down the information sheet and the consent form]. With your permission, I would like to audio record the interview because I don't want to miss out any of your comments. All responses will be kept confidential. This means that your de-identified interview responses will only be shared with research team members, and we will ensure that any information we include in our report or publications doesn't identify you as the respondent. You may decline to answer any question or stop the interview at any time and for any reason. Are there any questions about what I have just explained?

May I turn on the digital recorder?

Please note that this guide represents the main themes to be discussed with the participants and as such doesn't include the various prompts that may also be used (examples given for each question). Non-leading and general prompts will also be used, such as "Can you please tell me a little bit more about that?" and "What does that mean to you".

Establishing rapport

Before we begin, I would like to hear a little bit about yourself. What is your educational and professional background?

Recruitment process

Now I would like to ask you to think about a typical recruitment process.

1. Step by step, would you describe a typical recruitment process in your organization? *[Note if they mention any digital tool. Please note the phases they mention, and prompt below phases, if they aren't already mentioned by them].*

Prompts:

1. Job advertisement phase
 - i. What is important for you at this phase
2. CV screening phase
 - i. How do you screen CVs?
 - ii. What criteria are important at this phase?
 - iii. How do you assess who gets invited to an interview?
 - iv. What comes after the interview phase?

[Note if they mention any other phase].

2. How would you describe an ideal candidate for a typical starting position in your company?

Prompts: Can you give an example?

Can you think of a situation in which you figured out that you made the wrong choice?

3. What is your understanding of bias and fairness in general and in the workplace during the recruitment processes?

Prompt: Positive, negative bias.

4. What, if any, measures against bias/discrimination exist at your workplace do they work?

Use of AI/software programs during the recruitment process

Take note on whether they already mentioned any AI tool or software in Q.2. If they did, follow-up on that conversation (You told me that you used X...)

5. Do you make use of AI or any digital product/tool during any part of this process?

[Check how knowledgeable they are regarding digital tools and AI].

Prompts: Do you know whether some of these products are AI-based or not? Do you know how these products operate?

Follow-up on technical issues such as data training etc., only if the employer proves to have some knowledge about the operation of these systems.

Ask Q6 if the employer has knowledge in that area:

6. Do you know what the data in the tools are based on? Are these data based on past employee data, if not what data is it based on? If done manually, what do you look out for and based on what criteria?
7. Are AI/technological decisions automated or semi-automated, how is the final decision regarding worker hiring made? What is your opinion on automated or semi-automated AI decisions?

General prompt on this section if they don't make use of these tools: If no, why not and would you consider using them in the future?

The use of AI/software programs during the human resources management process

8. What about the human resources management process? Do you make use of AI or any digital tools in this process?

Prompts: Do you know whether some of these products are AI-based or not? Do you know how these products operate?

Outsourcing

9. Do you outsource any of these processes? If so, how well do technology developers make you understand their product and its use?

Prompt: How is the tool evaluated for promotional claims made (accuracy/efficacy)? Does the tool do what it's advertised for?

Opinions regarding the impact of AI on work processes

10. How does AI impact work processes?

Prompt: How does/might it have an impact on ensuring fairness in recruitment and HRM processes?

Conclusion

Mitigation strategies/best practices

My last question:

11. How best do you think AI can or should be used in recruitment and management (with regards to bias and fairness)?

Is there anything else that you would like to comment on about what we have discussed so far?

Thank you very much for your time and the information you shared today.

SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW GUIDE

EMPLOYEES

Introduction

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. We are interviewing you to better understand the recruitment and human resource management process in your company, your experience and perception of the process and the way in which the software used can affect the fairness of the recruitment and HRM processes. There are no right or wrong answers to any of our questions, we are interested in your own experience.

We have an information sheet and a consent form for you to sign. [Hand down the information sheet and the consent form]. With your permission, I would like to audio record the interview because I don't want to miss out any of your comments. All responses will be kept confidential. This means that your de-identified interview responses will only be shared with research team members, and we will ensure that any information we include in our report or publications doesn't identify you as the respondent. You may decline to answer any question or stop the interview at any time and for any reason. Are there any questions about what I have just explained?

May I turn on the digital recorder?

Please note that this guide represents the main themes to be discussed with the participants and as such doesn't include the various prompts that may also be used (examples given for each question). Non-leading and general prompts will also be used, such as "Can you please tell me a little bit more about that?" and "What does that mean to you".

Establishing rapport

Before we begin, I would like to hear a little bit about yourself.

What is your current position? And what is your professional and educational background?

Recruitment process

Now I would like to ask you to think about your experience of the recruitment process.

1. How was your recruitment process?

Prompt on different phases of recruitment. Note if they mention any digital tools/AI.

2. Did you experience any difficulties or barriers during the application and hiring process?

i. If yes, can you please briefly explain?

3. What is your understanding of (un)biased/fair/equal treatment in the workplace?

4. What is your perception on the use of AI/technology in recruitment?

Prompt: Taking into consideration the issue of bias/discrimination/fairness what is your opinion on the use of AI/technology in recruitment?

Management

5. Are you aware of how your organisation manages workers with regards to performance evaluation, sanctions, promotions etc.?

Prompts: Do you know the tools used to assess you?

Do you do self-assessments of your performance or colleague assessments (where colleagues are made to assess each other)?

Are you given explanations as to how you were assessed (performance, sanctions, promotions etc.)?

What is your opinion on how your organisation manages workers?

6. Do you have any concerns regarding fairness either for you or your colleagues when it comes to how your organisation manages workers (with or without AI/technology)?
7. What is your perception on the use of AI/technology in worker management?
8. Do you think the management process (performance evaluation, promotion, sanctions etc) is favourable or unfavourable to employees taking into consideration race/ethnicity/nationality, gender, and disability?

Mitigation strategies

9. How best do you think AI can or should be used in recruitment and management (with regards to bias and fairness)? Do you think AI needs to be regulated? If yes, by who?

My last question:

10. What other suggestions or thoughts do you have regarding the use of AI/technology in the workplace?

Is there anything else that you would like to comment on about what we have discussed so far?

Thank you very much for your time and the information you shared today.

SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW GUIDE

AI DEVELOPERS

Introduction

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this interview. We are interviewing you to

Better understand the recruitment and human resource management process in your company, your experience and perception of the process and the way in which the software used can affect the fairness of the recruitment and HRM processes. There are no right or wrong answers to any of our questions, we are interested in your own experience.

We have an information sheet and a consent form for you to sign. [Hand down the information sheet and the consent form]. With your permission, I would like to audio record the interview because I don't want to miss out any of your comments. All responses will be kept confidential. This means that your de-identified interview responses will only be shared with research team members, and we will ensure that any information we include in our report or publications doesn't identify you as the respondent. You may decline to answer any question or stop the interview at any time and for any reason. Are there any questions about what I have just explained?

May I turn on the digital recorder?

Please note that this guide represents the main themes to be discussed with the participants and as such doesn't include the various prompts that may also be used (examples given for each question). Non-leading and general prompts will also be used, such as "Can you please tell me a little bit more about that?" and "What does that mean to you".

Establishing rapport

Before we begin, I would like to hear a little bit about yourself.

- What is your current position? And what is your professional and educational background?

Developing the AI tool

Now I would like to ask you to think about your experience of developing the AI tool.

1. What is the process of developing an AI/tech tool for use in Human Resource (HR) practices?
2. What training data do you use to train your algorithms?
3. What criteria are used when choosing parameters for the algorithm?

Consideration for bias

4. What is your understanding of bias and fairness (in general and in the workplace)?
5. In what ways do you think bias can occur with the use of these AI/ technological tools in HRM (for recruitment or management)?
6. What considerations are made with regards to bias/fairness (mitigation) when developing AI tools/ how is fairness implemented?

AI ethics

7. What is your view on AI ethics and the ethical responsibility of AI developers?
 - a. What is your perception on how AI tools are promoted for use in HR Practices?

8. What are your thoughts on the rights of workers with regards to the implementation of AI in HR management
 - a. What do you think are the limitations of adopting AI in HR practices with regards to workers' rights?
 - b. How will you feel if your own company uses AI to recruit developers like you?

Mitigation strategies

9. How best do you think AI can or should be used in recruitment and management (with regards to bias and fairness)?
 - a. What should be avoided? What are your main concerns with AI development for HRM?

My last questions:

10. What other suggestions or thoughts do you have regarding the use of AI/technology in the workplace?
11. What do you think could be the role of AI in 2050?

Is there anything else that you would like to comment on about what we have discussed so far?

Thank you very much for your time and the information you shared today.

Annex 2 – Ethical clearance

Meldeskjema for behandling av personopplysninger

30/10/2023, 20:22

[Notification form](#) / [BIAS: Mitigating Diversity Biases of AI in the Labor Market](#) / Assessment

Assessment of processing of personal data

Reference number
991952**Assessment type**
Standard**Date**
15.08.2023**Title**

BIAS: Mitigating Diversity Biases of AI in the Labor Market

Institution responsible for the project

Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet / Det humanistiske fakultet / Institutt for tverrfaglige kulturstudier

Project leader

Roger A. Søråa

Project period

31.10.2022 - 30.10.2026

Categories of personal data

General

Special

Legal basis

Consent (General Data Protection Regulation art. 6 nr. 1 a)

Explicit consent (General Data Protection Regulation art. 9 nr. 2 a)

The processing of personal data is lawful, so long as it is carried out as stated in the notification form. The legal basis is valid until 30.10.2028.

[Notification Form](#)**Comment**

ABOUT OUR ASSESSMENT

Data Protection Services has an agreement with the institution where you are conducting research. As part of this agreement, we provide guidance so that the processing of personal data in your project is lawful and complies with data protection legislation. We have now assessed that you have a legal basis to process personal data in this project.

TYPE OF DATA

The project will process special categories of personal data about trade union membership.

LEGAL BASIS

Data subjects will consent to the processing of their personal data. The legal basis for processing is art. 6.1 a) of the GDPR. The data subjects in sample 3 (employees) will give their explicit consent to the processing of special categories of personal data. Thus, the conditions in art. 9.2 a) are met and the prohibition against processing special categories of personal data does not apply.

FOLLOW YOUR INSTITUTION'S GUIDELINES

You must store, send and secure the collected data in accordance with your institution's guidelines. This means that you must use data processors (and the like) that your institution has an agreement with (i.e. cloud storage, online survey, and video conferencing providers).

Our assessment presupposes that the project will meet requirements of accuracy (art. 5.1 d), integrity and confidentiality (art. 5.1 f) and security (art. 32) when processing personal data.

<https://meldeskjema.sikt.no/64390f30-aba2-424b-a347-47e8b11b2795/vurdering>

Page 1 of 2

NOTIFY CHANGES

If you intend to make changes to the processing of personal data in this project, it may be necessary to notify us. This is done by updating the information registered in the Notification Form. On our website we explain which changes must be notified. Wait until you receive an answer from us before you carry out the changes: <https://sikt.no/en/notify-changes-notification-form>

FOLLOW-UP OF THE PROJECT

We will follow up the progress of the project underway (every other year) and at the planned date for anonymisation, in order to determine whether the processing of personal data is being carried out in accordance with what is documented.

Good luck with the project!

Annex 3 Information sheet and consent form

BIAS PROJECT

This is an inquiry about participation in the BIAS research project (www.biasproject.eu), where the main purpose is to identify and mitigate diversity bias of AI applications in the labour market. In this letter we will give you information about the purpose of the project and what your participation will involve.

Purpose of the project

The BIAS project is funded by the European Commission under the Grant Agreement no. 101070468 and seeks to identify and mitigate diversity bias that occur when Artificial Intelligence is used in a human resources management context. In order to map knowledge on this topic, we want to interview you and other stakeholders who have thoughts on diversity biases in human resources management, have overseen human resources management, and/or have worked on AI applications. In this way, it will be possible to gain a nuanced understanding of what constitutes bias, how bias has been experienced, and how it can be mitigated through both technical and non-technical means. Based on these research findings, the BIAS Consortium will then develop and validate technology as well as develop capacity building curricula where stakeholders in the AI and HRM community can learn about the existence of AI bias, why it is important to address such bias, and some concrete tools for doing so.

Who is responsible for the research project?

The BIAS project is coordinated by the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) (Norway) and is composed of the following partners:

Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) (Norway); Berner Fachhochschule (Switzerland); Haskoli Islands (Iceland); Globaz, S.A. (Portugal); Crowdhelix Limited (Ireland); Smart Venice Srl (Italy); Universiteit Leiden (The Netherlands); Digiotech Ou (Estonia); Farplas Otomotiv Anonim Sirketi (Türkiye).

All the partners equally contribute to the implementation of the project activities according to their expertise.

Why are you being asked to participate?

You have been invited to participate in the BIAS project because you are identified as a stakeholder (employer, HR, employees, union representative, developers and/or NGOs) who have important thoughts on the topic BIAS investigates.

What does participation involve for you?

We are inviting you to be interviewed for the qualitative data collection of the project. The interview will focus primarily on AI tools for recruitment and management in the workplace, what bias can be present in the workplace and how this bias manifests itself, and how this is experienced by relevant stakeholders.

Participation is voluntary

Participation in the project activities is voluntary. If you chose to participate, you can withdraw your consent at any time, without giving a reason. Your personal privacy- how we will store and use your personal data

We will only use your personal data for the purpose specified in this information letter. We will process your personal data confidentially and in accordance with data protection legislation, namely GDPR. We will store your name and email address for the purpose of organizing the interview and documenting your consent. The interview will be voice recorded by the program "nettskjema diktafon app" and/or an external non-connected voice recorder unit. An anonymized transcript will be made from the recording. Following transcription, the voice recording will be destroyed. Only NTNU will have access to voice recordings; other project partners will have access only to anonymized transcripts. You will be given pseudonyms, and any quotes or views

attributed to you will be done in a way that it is not possible to identify you as the source, either in internal reports or in research publications. A scramble key table will be stored in a separate hand written log.

What will happen to your personal data at the end of the research project?

The BIAS project is scheduled to end on 31st October 2026. Your personal data will be retained for two years after this date for the purpose of documenting consent to the interview because of the audits the European Commission could conduct within this timeframe. The BIAS Consortium will then permanently erase all the personal data, in the sense that all of them will be made unusable and it will no longer be possible to restore them.

What gives us the right to process your personal data?

We will process your personal data based on your consent.

Based on an agreement with NTNU, The Data Protection Services of Sikt – Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research has assessed that the processing of personal data in this project meets requirements in data protection legislation.

What rights do I have?

So long as you can be identified in the collected data, you have the right to:

- access the personal data that is being processed about you
- request that your personal data is deleted
- request that incorrect personal data about you is corrected/rectified
- receive a copy of your personal data (data portability), and
- send a complaint to the Norwegian Data Protection Authority regarding the processing of your personal data

Where can I find out more?

If you have questions about the project, or want to exercise your rights, contact:

- NTNU via Project leader Roger A. Søråa, roger.soraa@ntnu.no or Project Administrator Mark Kharas, mark.w.kharas@ntnu.no

If you have questions about how data protection has been assessed in this project by Sikt, contact:

- email: (personverntjenester@sikt.no) or by telephone: +47 73 98 40 40.

Yours sincerely,
Roger A. Søråa
Project Leader

Consent Form

I am at least 18 years old, and I have received and understood information about the BIAS project. I have been informed about its data processing activities and the rights I am entitled to. Also, I have been given the opportunity to ask questions. Accordingly, I give consent:

- to participate in interview(s) for BIAS
- for the following personal data to be processed for the purpose of the BIAS project:
 - Name
 - Contact information (email)
 - Country of residence
 - Gender
 - Age-range in decades
 - Trade union membership
 - Voice recording
 - (Only include for Turkish interviews): For your voice recording to be transferred and stored outside Türkiye in the manner described above)
 - BIAS constituency (Worker, Workers' representatives, HR officer/manager, Representative of a network of HR officers/managers, Representative of a civil society organization/ NGO, AI specialist)
 - Institutional affiliation (if applicable)

(Name, signature, date)

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Consortium

NTNU

UNIVERSITY
OF ICELAND

LOBA®

CrowdHelix

SMARTVENCE

Universiteit
Leiden
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Bern University
of Applied Sciences

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